

INVESTIGATING OPTOMETRIC AND ORTHOPTIC CONDITIONS IN AUTISTIC ADULTS

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Project working title: Investigating optometric and orthoptic conditions in autistic adults.

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NHS Research Ethics Committee reference 271545.

A. Introduction

Background & rationale

Limited research has been conducted to investigate the links between autism and optometric and orthoptic conditions. Optometric and orthoptic conditions involve those commonly considered in an optometric examination, for example visual acuity, refractive error and the integrity of binocular vision.

The current literature on optometric conditions in autistic individuals, which is very limited, suggests they have a greater prevalence of binocular vision anomalies (Wang et al., 2018, Anketell et al., 2018, Gowen et al., 2017, Kabatus et al., 2015, Milne et al., 2009, Kaplan et al., 1999, Scharre & Creadon, 1992) and refractive error (Anketell et al., 2016, Gowen et al., 2017). This research has been conducted on autistic children and mostly those with co-existing learning disabilities; learning disabilities carry their own risk factors for optometric and orthoptic conditions. Little is known about the clinical presentation of adults with autism who do not have learning disabilities, and this population are the subject of this research.

It is worth considering that symptoms of a wide variety of optometric disorders (refractive mis-correction, binocular vision anomalies, visual stress) are very similar and may be interpreted as related to autism rather than vision. Furthermore, due to the sensory and communication difficulties an autistic individual experiences they may find a visit to an optometrist stressful, resulting in avoidance or incorrect test results.

Study aims & objectives

This project will focus on the investigation of optometric and orthoptic conditions in autistic adults without learning difficulties. The following objectives have been laid out:

1. To quantitatively describe the range and type of optometric conditions in autistic adults and suggest possible links with visual sensory symptoms;
2. To investigate the impact of treatment, if any, on vision, visual symptoms and quality of life**;
3. To develop guidelines and training for optometrists to provide more “autism-friendly” practice environments and eye examinations.

****Primary objective**

B. Methods

This study has received ethical approval from the NHS research ethics committee (IRAS ID 271545).

This study aims to determine the range and type of common optometric conditions in the autistic adult population who do not have learning disabilities. We will be investigating if any current correction worn is actually correct (based on the set criteria for power and tint colour in table 1). We also want to investigate the impacts of treating any anomalies which can involve spectacles, exercises and coloured tints. It is not necessary that the participant is experiencing any symptoms for treatment to be prescribed.

Participants

A power calculation (one-tailed t-test, repeated measures, medium effect size (0.6), 0.80 power) suggests we require a treatment group of 19 participants to investigate aim 2. The estimated prevalence rate of optometric conditions in autistic children is ~30-50% (Gowen et al., 2017). Therefore, taking into account the lower value of this prevalence rate, we will aim to recruit a sample of ~80 participants and obtain 70 full data sets. This number is also feasible for the time period available to conduct the study. The inclusion criteria will be as follows:

- Diagnosed as autistic*;
- Not diagnosed as learning disabled*;
- Aged 18 years or above;
- Being able to travel to the university.

**This will be evidenced by the participants' diagnosis documents which they will be asked to bring with them; this is relevant only to participants recruited from the local community and not NHS.*

The exclusion criteria will be as follows:

- Aged below 18 years;
- Diagnosis of a learning disability;
- Unable to communicate verbally;
- Unable to travel to the University.

Time-plan

The following time-plan is suggested, but may alter depending on participant recruitment:

1. Eye examinations from February 2020 till approximately December 2020.
2. Final follow up examinations from December 2020 till March 2021.
3. Data Analysis from April 2020 till end June 2021.

Recruitment

The study advert will be publicised by email and social media using the Autism@Manchester mailing list, Facebook and Twitter accounts, Autism@Manchester database, local autism groups who have opted to support this project and the University volunteering site.

Potential participants who have shown interest in and are suitable for this study will be sent the Participant information sheet (PIS). Once a participant confirms that they would like to take part in the study they will be booked in for an eye examination. They will also be sent a “what to expect during the study” document detailing the components of an eye examination tailored to this study; this document also contains video links which will demonstrate the tests.

For recruitment through the NHS, the study advert will be displayed in patient waiting areas, at post-diagnostic group sessions and in drop-in clinics. It will also be sent to the NHS staff mailing list. Clinicians in autism clinics will approach suitable patients about the study with flyers and take verbal consent for a member of the R&D team to contact them for further discussion. After being approached by a member of the R&D team patients can choose to contact the research optometrist by email or provide consent to contact to the R&D team.

Secondly, members of the research team will present talks at post-diagnostic group sessions and hand out flyers. Finally, the research team will attend drop-in sessions where they can distribute the study advert and speak to patients about the study. Once a participant confirms that they would like to take part in the study, having read the PIS, they will be booked in for an eye examination. They will also be sent the “what to expect during the study” document.

Participants who withdraw consent

Participants can withdraw consent at any time without giving any reason, as participation in the research is voluntary, without their care or legal rights being affected. However, data collected up until the point of withdrawal will still be used towards the study, and it will not be possible to remove data once it has been anonymised and forms part of the data set. This is clearly stated in the PIS.

Procedure

Study visits will take place at the University of Manchester Cary Bannister building. Participant attendance will be confirmed a day prior to the scheduled eye examination by email.

Upon arrival at the university, participants will be taken to the eye examination room and allowed time to become familiar with the room and equipment. They will also be offered refreshments. Here, each participant will be given the opportunity to re-read the PIS and ask any questions. They will then be asked to complete a consent form.

Once consent has been received from the participant, they will be asked to complete four questionnaires: a participant questionnaire, Visual Function 14 Quality of Life questionnaire (Steinberg et al., 1994), Convergence insufficiency symptoms survey (CITT, 2008) and Glasgow sensory questionnaire (Robertson and Simmons, 2013). The participant questionnaire will capture the following details:

1. Name
2. DoB
3. Gender
4. Address and contact details
5. Occupation
6. GP details

On completion of the questionnaires, the eye examination will begin, during which the following details will be noted on a paper record card:

1. Details of ocular health and visual symptoms
2. Optometric test results
3. Possible referral

The eye examination will consist of regular tests employed by optometrist and set protocols will be followed depending on the findings. Table 1 outlines the individual tests with the criteria for “normal” (where applicable). Table 2, coupled with table 3, where appropriate, describes the interventions which will be employed when findings fall outside the “normal” ranges. Although the prescription of intervention in practice is based on patient symptoms and test results, in this study we will only be basing this on the test results.

Table 1 The individual tests that will be conducted during the eye examination alongside the proposed "norms". The third and fourth column highlight if the test is relevant to the study or for completeness of the examination. The final column indicates the tests that will be repeated if a significant change in prescription is found.

Test	Procedure, "normal" values	Important for this study	Important for completeness of an EE	To repeated significant change prescription found
History & symptoms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any visual or eye problems? • How is your vision at distance/near/intermediate with or without glasses? Details of current glasses. • Last eye examination? What was the outcome there? Do you wear contact lenses? Last aftercare? • Ocular health: History of GP/hospital visit? Any underlying eye conditions? Did you have to wear a patch over one eye when you were younger? Any itchiness/ dryness/ stickiness? • General health: How is your general health? Any underlying health conditions? Do you take any medication? Any allergies? Do you smoke? • Family health: Any first-degree family members with any eye or health conditions? • Headaches/ flashes/ floaters/Diplopia? • Do you drive? With or without glasses? • What is your occupation? • Do you use any type of display screen? At what distance? Which position? How often? • Do you have any hobbies or play any sports? • Any other problems regarding your eyes or vision which we haven't talked about? 	*	*	
Distance and near unaided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the Thomson logMAR chart at distance and Bailey-Lovie at near (40cm). • "Normal" will be classed as up to 6/7.5 (0.1) according to the ICD-9-CM (CDC, 2013). At near, normal will be classed as up to N4 @ 40cm (0.1) taking into account the 	*	*	*

vision/ visual acuity	recommendations for “normal” for distance by the ICD-9-CM. The order of testing will be right eye, left eye, both eyes.			
Cover test (cover/uncover and alternate) at distance and near	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A translucent occluder will be used to cover the eyes. • At distance, the participant will be asked to focus on a letter one line above the poorest monocular unaided vision/ visual acuity (section of a letter if 6/12 or worse). • At near they will be asked to focus on a letter one level bigger than their poorest monocular unaided vision/ visual acuity at 40 cm (section of a letter if 20/40 or worse). • “Normal” will be classed as a heterophoria with an opposing fusional reserve which meets Sheard’s criterion and which has a “good” recovery and remains compensated on 8 covering/uncovering. “Good” recovery is defined as smooth and fast/moderate recovery movements. “Poor” is defined as jerky and slow recovery movements or recovery only on blink (Evans, 2007). • A strabismus and decompensating heterophoria will be classed as “abnormal”. • The size of any deviation will be determined using Maddox rod at distance and Thorrington at near. 	*	*	*
Ocular motility (double H pattern)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be conducted at approximately 50cm with a pen torch. The participant will be instructed to report any diplopia and pain. • “Normal” will be defined as a full and smooth ocular motility with no pain or diplopia. A/V patterns will also be noted. • In the case of diplopia occurring at any point then cover test will be performed in all direction of gaze. The amplitude of the deviation will be estimated and noted. • If findings indicate a pathological change in ocular motility which has not been found before then the participant will be emergency referred to the hospital. 		*	
Near point of convergence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be assessed using the line and spot target on the RAF rule. • Convergence insufficiency will be classed as one of: a near point of convergence >10cm (Evans & Doshi, 2001, Von Noorden & Campos, 2002), an exodeviation at near which is >4Δ greater than distance with the full refractive correction in place (CITT, 2008, Scheimann et al., 2005, Rouse et al., 1998) and a significant near base out fixation disparity (defined below). 	*		*

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Near point of convergence will be measured once. Diplopia will be demonstrated to the participant first on the RAF rule, then the official measure will be made. 			
Pupil reactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be assessed using an ophthalmoscope in a dark room. A burton lamp will be used in the case of dark irises. • The shape of the pupils, relative sizes and reactions to light and accommodation will be noted (PERRLA) and assessed for relative afferent pupillary defect. • Any physiological variations, e.g. pupil shape, and difference in sizes consistent in light and dark conditions will be noted. • Any explainable cause for a relative afferent pupillary defect, e.g. monocular cataract, will be noted. • Any findings indicating a recently acquired pupil defect, e.g. Adies pupil or Horner's syndrome, or unexplainable relative afferent pupillary defect will be referred to the Hospital. • Any longstanding pupil defect which is known to the participant will not be actioned. 		*	
Distance objective (retinoscopy) and subjective refraction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Firstly, distance and near pupillary distance will be measured and noted. • Retinoscopy will be performed with the participant looking towards the green section of the duochrome. The other eye will be appropriately fogged. • Next, best sphere will be performed followed by duochrome. The participant will be kept on the green. • Next will be cross-cylinder assessment followed by the +1.00 blur test. • For the +1.00 blur test, a response between 6/12 and 6/19 will be accepted as long as it is the SAME as the fellow eye. • Finally, visual acuity will be noted. For visual acuities 6/9 or worse pinhole acuity will be checked. • The maximum possible plus prescription will be the endpoint. These steps will all be repeated for the other eye. • The Humphriss binocular balance technique will be performed followed by binocular addition. 	*	*	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cumberland et al (2015) defined myopia as $\leq -0.50\text{DS}$ and hyperopia as $\geq +0.50\text{DS}$ (MSE) in their study. Refraction repeatability of an individual clinician is within 0.25D in 80% of cases and between clinicians can be up to 0.75D (Elliott & Howell-Duffy, 2015). Taking these two investigations into account, new glasses will only be dispensed if the refraction is at least or differs by at least $\pm 0.50\text{DS}$ or $\pm 0.50\text{DC}$ and cylinder axis changes are outside the British standard tolerances: <table border="1" data-bbox="577 438 1668 587"> <tr> <td>Absolute cylindrical power dioptries</td> <td>$\geq 0,125$ and $\leq 0,25$</td> <td>$> 0,25$ and $\leq 0,50$</td> <td>$> 0,50$ and $\leq 0,75$</td> <td>$> 0,75$ and $\leq 1,50$</td> <td>$> 1,50$ and $\leq 2,50$</td> <td>$> 2,50$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tolerance on the axis direction degrees</td> <td>± 16</td> <td>± 9</td> <td>± 6</td> <td>± 4</td> <td>± 3</td> <td>± 2</td> </tr> </table> <p>This will be defined as a “significant” change in prescription.</p>	Absolute cylindrical power dioptries	$\geq 0,125$ and $\leq 0,25$	$> 0,25$ and $\leq 0,50$	$> 0,50$ and $\leq 0,75$	$> 0,75$ and $\leq 1,50$	$> 1,50$ and $\leq 2,50$	$> 2,50$	Tolerance on the axis direction degrees	± 16	± 9	± 6	± 4	± 3	± 2			
Absolute cylindrical power dioptries	$\geq 0,125$ and $\leq 0,25$	$> 0,25$ and $\leq 0,50$	$> 0,50$ and $\leq 0,75$	$> 0,75$ and $\leq 1,50$	$> 1,50$ and $\leq 2,50$	$> 2,50$												
Tolerance on the axis direction degrees	± 16	± 9	± 6	± 4	± 3	± 2												
<p>Distance fixation disparity with refractive correction in place</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aligning prism will be measured using the Mallett box. Vertical will be performed before horizontal, and individually. The participant will be clearly instructed to focus on the centre of the cross and report the alignment status of the Nonius markers. Jenkins et al (1989) defined a significant fixation disparity more likely to cause symptoms as requiring an aligning prism $\geq 1\Delta$ for pre-presbyopes and $\geq 2\Delta$ in presbyopes. Normal will be classed according to this criterion horizontally. No vertical fixation disparity will be accepted as normal. For individuals with a strabismus, the Bagolini lenses will be used to check binocular status. 	*		*														
<p>Amplitude of accommodation binocular and monocular</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Will be measured using the RAF rule and push-up method. The participant will be asked to focus on an N5 sized target. “Normal” will be classed as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upto 20 years old: $\geq 10.00\text{D}$ Upto 30 years old: $\geq 7.50\text{D}$ Upto 40 years old: $\geq 5.00\text{D}$ (Evans, 2007). The monocular amplitudes being within 0.50D of each other and lower than the binocular amplitude. 	*		*														

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before taking the official measurements, “blur” will be demonstrated to the participant on the RAF rule. • To ensure we get a measurement as close to threshold as possible, the participant will be asked if they can focus the target again when they report blur each time. • An investigation for a need for a near addition (presbyopia) will be classified as a binocular amplitude less than 4.50D. 			
Accommodative lag	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the Knott method @ 25cm. • Will ONLY be performed in “pre-presbyopes”. Leon et al (2017) found the accommodative lag to increase after 40 years of age as is expected due to presbyopia (Amplitude of accommodation <4.50D). • The American Optometric Association (2011) has quoted the “normal” range of accommodative lag to be +0.25D to +0.75D. This will be the criteria for “normal” in this study. • If a negative value is found, then the distance refraction will be rechecked. 	*		*
Accommodative facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be assessed in individuals with an amplitude of accommodation $\geq 4.50D$ only. • A 20 second training on the test will be given prior to commencing the measurements. • Will be assessed using the +/-2.00DS flipper assessment, using N5 number targets at 40cm. • Normal will be classified as 11 cycles per minute monocular and 8 cycles per minute binocular, adapted from Zeller et al's (1984) criteria. • The order of testing will be right eye, left eye, both eyes. 	*		*
Near word vision testing and near addition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The near visual acuity will be measured to threshold with the Bailey-Lovie test (at 40cm) and only their distance refractive correction in place. The order of testing will be right eye, left eye, both eyes. • For individuals with an amplitude of accommodation $\geq 4.50D$, if the near visual acuity N4 or better @ 40cm no further action will be taken. If it is outside this normal range then it will be closely investigated using the accommodation tests described in this table and treatment given according to the abnormality found. 	*	*	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For individuals with an amplitude of accommodation $<4.50D$, the following equation will be followed for prediction of near addition power: $Near\ Add\ (D) = WD\ (D) - 2/3AoA\ (D)$. • The predicted near addition will be added over the distance refraction and near acuity checked again. $\pm 0.25DS$ flippers will be used binocularly to check if the near acuity can be improved. • The final near add will be determined using the near duochrome. The participant will be kept slightly on the green to ensure a good near range. The minimum add recommended will be $+0.75DS$. For existing near adds, a new near prescription will only be recommended if a change of at least $\pm 0.50DS$ is found in the near prescription after confirmation with the near duochrome. 			
Near fixation disparity with near refractive correction and any distance prisms in place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aligning prism will be measured using the Mallett unit at the participants habitual working distance. Vertical will be performed before horizontal and individually. The participant will be clearly instructed to focus on the centre of the cross and report the alignment status of the Nonius markers. • Jenkins et al (1989) defined a significant fixation disparity more likely to cause symptoms as requiring an aligning prism $\geq 1\Delta$ for “pre-presbyopes” and $\geq 2\Delta$ in “presbyopes”. Normal will be classed according to this criterion horizontally. Any fixation disparity vertically will not be accepted as normal. • For individuals with a strabismus, the Bagolini lenses will be used to check binocular status. 	*		*
Stereopsis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be performed with the full near correction in place including any significant aligning prism. • Will be assessed using the TNO. • According to Piano et al (2016) the normal upper limit for TNO is 120 seconds of arc. This will be the criteria for “normal” in this study. • An abnormal stereoacuity will be due to strabismus, amblyopia, an abnormal heterophoria at near, an accommodative problem. 	*		*
Colour vision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be assessed using the City University test mark 2 on all participants. 	*		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It will be conducted monocularly; right eye, left eye. • Any colour vision defect will be classed as abnormal. • If a colour vision defect is found and the participant is aware of it, no action will be taken. • If a new colour vision defect is found, the participant will be referred to Further investigative techniques clinic for further investigation. 			
Pattern glare test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Those prone to pattern glare will experience problems on the 3 cycles per degree plate, but participants will be assessed on all 3 plates. <4 distortions on 3 cycles per degree plate is normal. If more are experienced, the participant is likely to suffer visual stress and benefit from coloured tints (Evans & Stevenson, 2008). • Each plate will be presented for 5 seconds @ 40cm. If 4 or more distortions are reported on the 3 cycles per degree plate then colorimetry will be performed. 	*		*
Prism fusion range	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be assessed using a prism bar at distance and near. Before taking the official measurements diplopia will be demonstrated to the participant. • With the refractive correction in place for distance, the participant will be asked to focus on a letter from a line of letters matching their binocular distance visual acuity for distance fusion range testing. For near fusion range testing, the participant will be asked to focus on a letter from a line of letters matching their binocular near visual acuity @ 40cm. • Order of testing: Base out, Base up/down, Base in. • For each, blur, break and recovery points will be noted. • “Normal” will be judged as an opposing fusional reserve to blur which is at least double the phoria size. 	*		*
IOP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be measured using the iCare tonometer. • As per the NICE guidelines (2017), any Intraocular pressure of up to 23mmHg will be accepted as normal. A difference of up to 3mmHg between the two eyes will be accepted as normal. 		*	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the intraocular pressure repeatedly falls outside these stated norms then the measurement will be repeated after 20 mins. If the intraocular pressure is still abnormal then clinical protocol will be followed. 			
Visual fields	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be assessed monocularly on all participants using the Henson MSST program. • If any abnormalities are found then the participant will be required to repeat the test. Interpretation and management will be based on clinical judgement. 		*	
Ocular health assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will be assessed with slit lamp, Volk or direct ophthalmoscopy and OCT. • The following will be assessed and noted: Lids & lashes, Conjunctiva, Cornea, tear film with fluorescein staining, anterior chamber, Van Herricks, iris, lens, vitreous & Shaffer's sign, optic nerve CD ratio, optic nerve margins, optic nerve colour, optic nerve rim thickness in 4 positions, Vessels & AV ratio, macula integrity, general appearance of the fundus. • Normal tear break-up time will be classed as ≥ 10 seconds. • Management will be based on clinical judgement of the noted findings and may require referral to further investigative techniques clinic, GP or Hospital. 		•	

Order of tests:

1. History and Symptoms
2. Distance unaided vision
3. Distance cover test
4. Near unaided vision
5. Near cover test
6. Ocular motility
7. Pupil reactions
8. IOP
9. Distance objective and subjective refraction
10. Maddox rod and distance fixation disparity
11. Distance prism fusion range
12. Amplitude of accommodation
13. (Accommodative lag)
14. (Accommodative facility)
15. (Near addition)
16. Near word vision
17. Thorington and near fixation disparity
18. Stereopsis
19. Near prism fusion range
20. Pattern glare
21. Near point of convergence
22. Colour vision
23. Ocular health
24. Visual fields
25. Ocular imaging
26. (Colorimetry)

After completion of this full eye examination, the participants' current spectacles, if any, will be checked for:

- Prescription
- Centration (compared to British tolerances)
- Coatings and tints

If there is a significant change in prescription found, then the marked tests in table 1 will be repeated with the habitual correction in place.

The first visit will conclude with a summary of the findings and prescription of treatment if required. Treatment can be new spectacles, not to wear spectacles, optometric exercises, precision tinted lenses (see table 2). Please note that the effect of a refractive correction on any suspected binocular vision anomalies will be confirmed before prescribing optometric exercises. Prism will only be considered in cases of vertical deviations, or where optometric exercises may not be possible or if optometric exercises fail. Tints/ coatings/ photochromic lenses will be added to any new spectacles if they exist on the habitual correction.

The participant will be handed a copy of their spectacle prescription upon completion of the eye examination alongside any appropriate leaflets/ information, supplied by the College of Optometrists or University optometry clinics, e.g. dilation leaflet, AMD leaflet etc as part of a

portfolio. If there are any findings during the examination which require participant referral to their GP or a hospital eye service this will be done after obtaining their verbal consent. A copy of the referral letter will be given to the participant. Exclusion on the basis of a participant being referred will be judged on a case-by-case basis. If the reason for referral is likely to influence the participant's vision then they will be excluded from follow up visits. However, the data obtained from the first visit will still be used towards data analysis.

During the eye examination, the participant will be asked three questions at specified points:

1. Are there any tests that you did not like? Why? (STOP)
2. What could have been improved about the ways these tests were conducted? (START)
3. Was there anything you liked about the way in which these tests were carried out? (CONTINUE)

The specified points will be:

1. After IOP
2. After distance prism fusion range
3. After near prism fusion range
4. After colour vision
5. After ocular health examination
6. After colorimetry

In addition to these questions, at the end of the first visit the participant will be asked if the video/ what to expect document had given them a realistic idea of the visit.

The responses to these questions will be audio recorded on an encrypted device so that they can be listened to and content analysed. The audio recordings will be transferred to the RDS as soon as possible and saved under the participant ID number.

Visit 1 considerations

Some participants may prefer to split visit 1 into two parts. This may be because doing all of these tests in one session may be tiring or overwhelming or may not fit their schedule. Although one session is preferred by the research team, participants will have the option to split visit 1 into two sessions. In this case, consent taking, questionnaires and tests 1-22 will be conducted at session one, and any repeat tests required if the participant is currently wearing spectacles. Tests 23-26 will be conducted at session two alongside dispensing any required spectacles or teaching of any exercises. Only at session two will the participants be given their spectacle prescription.

Table 2 Treatment options for any “abnormal” findings in the tests in table 1

Anomaly	Type of treatment	Specific treatment
Distance refractive error requiring new spectacles	spectacles	Single vision distance
Near addition only	spectacles	Single vision near
Distance refractive error and a near addition	spectacles	Single vision distance and near Bifocals Varifocals
Significant aligning prism post refraction	exercises	Exercises are only suitable for horizontal fixation disparity; vertical fixation disparity would need correction with prism. Distance: appropriate physiological diplopia exercise (see: table 3) Near: appropriate physiological diplopia exercise (see: table 3)
	Prism	Incorporation of prism into selected lens type.
Convergence insufficiency if persistent with refractive correction.	exercises	Appropriate physiological diplopia exercise (see: table 3)
	Prisms	Only if no improvement with exercises after 4 weeks. The minimum prism required to align the bars on the near Mallett unit when held at the participants habitual working distance. Single vision near
Accommodative insufficiency(pre-presbyopes)	Exercises	Hart Chart Additional exercise (if required): Dot card with accommodative targets.

	Spectacles	SVN only if no improvement with exercises after 4 weeks. Add will be of the value required to improve the participants lag to normal limits.
Abnormal accommodative lag (pre-presbyopes)	exercises	Hart Chart Additional exercise (if required): Jump accommodation (+/-2.00DS flippers)
	spectacles	Single vision near with minimum near positive add to bring lag into normal range. Confirmed lead: Single vision near with minimum near negative add to bring into normal range.
Accommodative infacility	Exercises	Hart chart Additional exercises (if required): Jump accommodation (+/-2.00DS flippers).
Abnormal heterophoria	exercises	if the abnormal heterophoria is persistent with the refractive correction in place. Appropriate physiological diplopia exercise (see: table 3)
	Prisms	Prescribe prism from Mallett, AT DISTANCE AND NEAR. Vertical fixation disparity cannot be treated with exercises and so prism will be prescribed first hand to correct this.
Visual stress	PTLs	If an insignificant spectacle prescription is found then precision tinted lenses will be prescribed straight away. If a significant spectacle prescription is found, precision tinted lenses will be prescribed after 1 month of successful plain spectacle wear.
Prism fusion range	exercises	Appropriate physiological diplopia exercise (see: table 3)
	prism	Recheck aligning prism on mallet unit and prescribe.

Table 3 physiological diplopia exercises in order of increasing difficulty

1	2 Pens
2	Brock string
3	Dot card
4	3 cats

Treatment specific details

Spectacles. For this study, all participants who are dispensed spectacles will be followed-up after a period of 1 month of wear. The follow-up appointment will be according to figure 2.

Figure 1 A flowchart of the follow-up procedure for dispensed spectacles

Optometric exercises. Optometric exercises will be recommended to improve any binocular vision anomalies if they are not resolved with a new refractive correction after 1 month, for example convergence insufficiency. As would be the case in practice, the participants will be asked to complete the exercises for five minutes, three times per day and to ensure compliance they will receive reminders via text message/ email weekly. The recall appointment will be after 1 month; at the recall appointment(s) the following will be done (figure 3):

Figure 2 a flowchart of the follow-up procedure for prescribed exercises

For participants prescribed prism, the follow up regime for spectacles will be employed with the added binocular vision tests.

Colorimetry. If no significant change is found in the spectacle prescription and positive pattern glare result is found, then colorimetry will be performed. The tint will be given with the habitual correction prescription. If the participant is prescribed a new pair of spectacles and also has a positive pattern glare result, at their 1-month spectacle recall colorimetry will be performed and appropriate tinted spectacles prescribed. If no significant prescription is found but a positive pattern glare result, then plano precision tinted spectacles will be prescribed. All participants dispensed with precision tinted lenses will be recalled after 1 month; figure 4 is a flowchart of the follow-up procedure:

Figure 3 a flowchart of the follow-up procedure for colorimetry

Participant discharge

- All participants will be required to attend the university after 3 months of their final intervention to complete the questionnaires again.
- Participants who are not prescribed any treatment at the initial eye examination will be followed-up after 3 months to act as a control measure. They will complete the questionnaires only and then discharged.
- If at the end of the study period any participants' abnormal findings have not been fully resolved they will be referred to the relevant Optometry clinic in the Carys Bannister building for continuing care.

C. Analysis plan

Data analysis will take place at the university and will be conducted by the research optometrist KRP. EG will have control of the data generated in this study. The data analysis plan has been laid out according to the project aims. The hypotheses have also been separated by aim. Please note, this study has both exploratory and confirmatory elements.

1. To quantitatively describe the range and type of optometric conditions in autistic adults and suggest possible links with visual sensory symptoms.
 - **Hypothesis 1:** We will find a variety of optometric conditions in our sample.
 - **Hypothesis 2:** We will find a clinically significant number of our participants to have a habitual refractive mis-correction.
 - **Hypothesis 3:** We will find a clinically significantly greater prevalence of binocular vision anomalies and refractive error in our sample when compared to neurotypical data (where possible).
 - **Hypothesis 4:** There will be a positive link between GSQ vision-scores and optometric findings outside the expected range in this study.

The percentage of cases of individual optometric anomalies found at the initial examinations will be calculated and presented in frequency tables. These will include binocular vision anomalies, visual stress and significant refractive error. These will be descriptively compared to the general population prevalence values, where available.

The percentage of participants dispensed with a new refractive correction, eye exercises or precision tinted lenses will be presented in a frequency table.

Rasch analysis allows transformation of non-linear response item scales to be placed on a numerical interval scale. Scores from the vision-related GSQ questions obtained at the initial visit will be Rasch analysed and then allocated into two groups: "low" and "high". The scores that determine these categories will be adapted from the results of Robertson (2012).

The proportion of participants in these low and high groups with the following categorical visual statuses will be calculated:

- a. those with strabismus;
- b. those with significant refractive error (defined by our set criteria in this study in terms of power/ cyl axis);
- c. those with a significant refractive miscorrection (defined by our set criteria in this study in terms of change in power/ cyl axis);
- d. those with amblyopia;
- e. those with visual stress (defined by a pattern glare score of ≥ 4 on pattern 2);
- f. those with a significant fixation disparity at distance (defined as requiring an aligning prism $\geq 1\Delta$ for pre-presbyopes and $\geq 2\Delta$ in presbyopes horizontally, and ANY magnitude of aligning prism vertically);
- g. those with a significant fixation disparity at near (defined as requiring an aligning prism $\geq 1\Delta$ for pre-presbyopes and $\geq 2\Delta$ in presbyopes horizontally, and ANY magnitude of aligning prism vertically);

- h. those with an uncompensated distance heterophoria (defined as an opposing fusional reserve to blur which is less than double the heterophoria size);
- i. those with an uncompensated near heterophoria (defined as an opposing fusional reserve to blur which is less than double the heterophoria size);
- j. those with a level of stereoacuity outside the normal range (defined as worse than 120");
- k. those with a positive result for a convergence insufficiency (defined as one of: a near point of convergence >10cm, an exodeviation at near which is >4Δ greater than distance with the full refractive correction in place or a significant near base out fixation disparity);
- l. those with a level of distance habitual acuity outside the normal range (defined as worse than 0.10 logMAR).

These will be χ^2 tested to decide if there is a significant difference in the proportion of participants who fall into the "high" and "low" groups for each categorical category.

From these individual analyses, the three factors with the most "significant difference in proportion" will be used as the independent variables in multiple regression analysis, and the GSQ score for the vision-related questions as the dependent variable. The most appropriate type of multiple regression analysis will be selected depending on the factors used (for example a multiple regression analysis suitable for categorical data or continuous data). Various rules of thumb have been suggested for the number of factors for regression analysis (Burmeister & Aitken, 2012); as per the 20:1 (participants:factors) rule, suggested by the Department of biostatistics at Vanderbilt University (2019), with our minimum target sample of 70 participants we should use three factors.

2. To investigate the impact of treatment, if any, on vision, visual symptoms and quality of life.
 - **Hypothesis 1:** There will be a significant difference in vision function, visual symptoms or quality of life between the first and final visit for participants who do receive treatment compared to those who do not receive treatment. The change in questionnaire score between these visits for the treatment group is expected to reflect an improvement.
 - **Hypothesis 2:** Linked to hypothesis 1, the questionnaire scores for the treatment group and non-treatment group are expected to differ at the first visit (with the "treatment" group suggesting more symptoms), but final visit questionnaire scores will suggest no significant difference.

All three questionnaires (GSQ, VF-14 QoL, CISS) will be completed by participants at the first and final visit.

Upon receiving all questionnaire data, statistical significance of any difference in questionnaire scores between the first and final visit will be tested. After careful consideration, we have decided correction for multiple comparisons will not be required as, as per Armstrong (2014), the results of the individual tests are important for this study and the following analyses have been carefully planned according to each hypothesis for this aim. Analysis will be as follows:

- a. Each questionnaire will be Rasch analysed; for the GSQ this will just be the vision-related questions. After this, the adjusted scores from each questionnaire for each individual participant will be calculated.
- b. The distribution of the data will be confirmed by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and visual inspection.
- c. If data is parametric:
 - a. ANOVA tests with factors of group (treatment, non treatment) and x visit (first, final) will be used to determine any significant difference in each questionnaire score between the first and final visit.
 - b. Significant interactions will be followed up using (a) paired t-tests to determine any significant difference between the first and final visit, for each group, and (b) independent t-tests to determine any significant difference in questionnaire scores between the treatment and non-treatment group at the first, and the final visits.
- d. If data is non-parametric:
 - a. Wilcoxon signed rank tests will be used to determine any significant difference between the first and final visit, for each group.
 - b. Mann Whitney tests will be used to determine any significant difference in questionnaire scores between the treatment and non-treatment group at the first, and the final visits.

*Please note, this analysis will only be possible for participants who have completed both the visit 1 and final visit questionnaires. Participants may not complete both sets of questionnaires due to:

- Exclusion due to referral for OH issues;
- Participants not attending to complete the final set of questionnaires;
- Participants requiring ongoing treatment which will last beyond the study.

3. To develop guidelines and training for optometrists to provide more “autism-friendly” practice environments and eye examinations.

- **Question 1:** How can eye examinations be made more “autism-friendly”?

Audio recordings of the feedback received during the initial visit will be analysed by inductive category formation content analysis (Mayring, 2014), using an exploratory approach. This is an appropriate analysis approach as it focuses only on data relevant to the research question and results in the development of summarising categories or codes (Mayring, 2014). It gives a true description of the dataset without being biased (Mayring, 2014). Frequencies that each code appeared in the dataset will also be documented. Categories or codes will finally be grouped into main categories or themes. Figure 4 is a flow chart by Mayring (2014) describing the steps involved in inductive category formation.

The analysis will result in a number of main categories relating to the participant feedback of the eye examinations. These will be used to design a set of guidelines for optometrists as to how they can provide more “autism-friendly” services in practice. This will also include feedback given on our specially prepared “what to expect” resources.

Figure 4 A flowchart of the steps involved in inductive category formation (Mayring, 2014).

Has data collection begun for this project?

- Yes

If data collection has begun, have you looked at the data?

- No

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